

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

D6.4 ATHENA e-platform for action

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: IMPLEMENTING GENDER EQUALITY PLANS TO UNLOCK RESEARCH POTENTIAL OF RPOS AND RFOS IN EUROPE

Grant Agreement n°: 101006416

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

info@athenaequality.eu
www.athenaequality.eu

Version history

Version	Date	Comments / Changes	Author/ Reviewer
0.1	23.02.22	Draft version sent to the Steering Committee	Cira Mendoza, Michelle Perello, Tamara Ventura, Omar González
0.2	25.02.22	Second draft version including comments from the Steering Committee	Steering Committee
1.0	28.02.22	Final version submitted to the EC	Coordinator

Document Information

Project Acronym	ATHENA
Project Title	Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe
Project Number	101006416
Instrument	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans
Project Start Date	01/02/2021
Project Duration	48 months
Work Package	WP6
Task	T6.3
Deliverable	D6.4 ATHENA e-platform for action
Due Date	28/02/2022
Submission Date	28/02/2022
Dissemination Level¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	PP1 – Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation (CE)
Version	1.0
Status	Final
Author(s)	Cira Mendoza, Michelle Perello, Tamara Ventura, Omar González
Reviewers	Steering Committee

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Table of Contents

List of Figures	3
Acronyms and Abbreviations	3
1. A web-based community platform for ATHENA	4
2. The ATHENA e-platform promoting project results and tools towards gender equality in R&I.....	4
2.1 Objectives of the ATHENA e-platform	4
2.2 Description of the e-platform	5
2.3 e-platform access.....	7
3. ATHENA e-platform webpages	9
3.1 ATHENA e-platform Homepage	9
3.2 Trainings section	11
3.3 'Women researchers' database section.....	15
3.3 'ATHENA Toolkit' section	17
3.4 'Community' section	18

List of Figures

Figure 1. Registration and log in to the e-platform.....	8
Figure 2. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (1/4).....	9
Figure 3. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (2/4).....	10
Figure 4. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (3/4).....	10
Figure 5. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (4/4).....	11
Figure 6. Main Training section (1/3).....	12
Figure 7. Main Training section (2/3).....	12
Figure 8. Example of a selected training	14
Figure 9. Lecture webpage	15
Figure 10. Women researchers' database page 1/2.....	16
Figure 11. Women researchers' database page 2/2.....	17
Figure 12. Interactive public forum	19

Acronyms and Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GEPI Committees	Gender Equality Plan Implementation (GEPI) Committees
Q&A	Questions and answers
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
T	Task
WP	Work package

1. A web-based community platform for ATHENA

The ATHENA project is funded by the European Commission (EC) under the topic of the *Science with and for Society* work programme SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 ‘*Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans*’. ATHENA overall aims at supporting the development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in 6 research performing organisations (RPOs) and 2 research funding organisations (RFOs) in Europe. To that purpose, Work Package (WP) 6 (named ‘*Sustainability strategy to ensure replication of GEPs and project results*’) includes a specific task (T6.3) titled ‘*Creation and maintenance of a web-based community platform with all project results and tools*’, whose aim is to host the materials and tools developed by the project at the same time as serving as a repository for identification of women researchers at EU level and a place for information and experiences exchange on GEPs and gender equality in science and research.

The ‘*ATHENA e-platform for action*’ is the result of this task, led by the Spanish SME Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L (short name, Consulta Europa). Consulta Europa developed the e-platform and included modifications and improvements based on comments received from the project consortium.

The present document briefly presents the e-platform, its objectives (section 2), description (section 2.2), access (section 2.3) and its webpages (section 3).

2. The ATHENA e-platform promoting project results and tools towards gender equality in R&I

2.1 Objectives of the ATHENA e-platform

The *ATHENA e-platform for action* (hereinafter referred to as e-platform) is a central means, together with the project website (www.athenaequality.eu), to publicly share the project material, advances and results. Specifically, the e-platform includes tools that contribute to achieve gender equality in science and research by:

- Sharing the material developed by the project, like the trainings that have been carried out so far and further trainings and webinars that will be implemented throughout the project.
- Supporting the visibility of women researchers and communicating their achievements (open-source database/compendium of women researchers at EU level).
- Providing a toolkit with an array of tools and resources that may assist project institutions with examples, guidance and inspiration useful for tailoring their institutional GEPs (ATHENA Toolkit).

- Facilitating the exchange of experiences and information in the field of gender equality in research and innovation and more specifically in the development and implementation of organisational GEPs ('Community' section/webpage which includes a Q&A interactive forum).

2.2 Description of the e-platform

In line with the above-mentioned in section 2.1, the ATHENA e-platform is already structured in the following pages/sections:

- Trainings.
- Women researchers.
- ATHENA Toolkit.
- Community.

The ATHENA e-platform will be constantly updated with new material and tools as the project progress. The women researcher's database and the Toolkit will be continuously populated and efforts will be put in place to keep the forum active throughout the project duration. Overall, the e-platform will be kept online throughout the project lifespan and for at least two years after the project has finished.

2.2.1 'Trainings' section

The 'Trainings' section already includes the recordings and material of the trainings that have been developed and carried out so far under the project framework. These trainings are those that have been implemented under task (T) 'T3.2 – Capacity building for GEPI Committees' for the project Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees. Further trainings that will be implemented under 'T3.3– Gender training programme' will be also shared within this section.

Further description and screenshots of the appearance and visual elements of this section are presented within section 3.2.

2.2.2 'Women researchers' section

As for the section 'Women researchers', this section includes a compendium/database of women researchers in Europe to contribute to make them visible and communicate their achievements. The database is open, and any user of the e-platform may contribute by submitting a request that is available within this section. Once the veracity of the data provided is proven, the profile of the women researcher will be published.

The data provided are also mapped so women researchers may be also identified in terms of geographical location.

More details about the specificities of this section and how the information is available therein may be found within section 3.2.

2.2.2 'ATHENA Toolkit' section

The 'ATHENA Toolkit' is aimed at supporting ATHENA RPOs and RFOs institutions that are in the process of developing their GEPs. The content of this section is reported within project deliverable '*D4.3 – ATHENA Toolkit for transforming the institutional change in terms of gender aspects*'. For this purpose, the toolkit offers an array of tools and resources that may assist project institutions with examples, guidance and inspiration useful for tailoring their institutional plans. This Toolkit should be used as complement of the '*D4.1-Best practice compendium*' project deliverable, which introduces relevant measures and actions identified across Europe research organisations for culture transformation and the development of GEPs.

The recommendations, resources and tools included within the toolkit may also serve any other research organisation interested in implementing a transformative change towards gender equality.

The tools and resources of the Toolkit already compile 74 resources, of which 20 are reports and 54 dynamic resources like videos, webinars, trainings, etc. The resources are organized according to the five content-related thematic areas recommended by the EC (i.e., Work-life balance and organizational culture; gender balance in leadership and decision-making; Gender equality in recruitment and career progression; Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content; Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment).

Further information about the ATHENA Toolkit may be found within the project deliverable '*D4.3 – ATHENA Toolkit for transforming the institutional culture in terms of gender aspects*'.

2.2.3 'Community' section

The 'Community' section includes an interactive forum to empower women and men to freely discuss the issues of gender equality in research and science. Particularly, the forum provides an opportunity for the ATHENA RPOs and RFOs that will implement their GEPs and other EU research organizations to discuss the specific challenges related to their transformative cultural change and specific issues on the development and implementation of their GEPs at the same time as sharing promising initiatives for promoting gender equality and diversity.

This section also includes a Questions and Answers (Q&A) forum where the project coordinator and selected representatives of the ATHENA project will answer to the questions of partner organisations and other interested stakeholders.

The above-mentioned provisions are shared publicly and are visible within the interactive forum to any user of the e-platform. Nevertheless, the forum also contains a private section which is only visible for the members of the ATHENA consortium. This private section is distributed into 9 rooms, one devoted to each of the 8 ATHENA institutions implementing a GEP and an additional one for the whole consortium. Within these rooms, consortium members and more specifically the ATHENA GEPI Committees members will discuss on GEPs development and implementation issues.

Further details and screenshots showing the appearance of this section may be found in section 3.

2.3 e-platform access

The ATHENA e-platform may be accessed by the link below:

<https://www.gender-equality.eu/>

2.3.1 Registration

To be able to interact within the e-platform, visitors should be previously registered and logged. To do so, visitors should follow the following steps:

1. Please go to <https://www.gender-equality.eu/> and click on the 'Register' button you may find at the top right section of the site. Once completed the registration fields, you should click on the 'Submit' button.
2. An automatic email will be sent to the inserted email account for verification. Please, confirm your registration by clicking on the link received. Note that if the confirmation link is not found within the inbox, it might be entered to the spam box.
3. After you have confirmed your email, you should go again to the ATHENA e-platform www.gender-equality.eu and log in by clicking on the 'Login' button at the top right. Then, fill the available fields and click on the 'Login' button.

athena
gender equality to unlock
research potential

Figure 1. Registration and log in to the e-platform

3. ATHENA e-platform webpages

3.1 ATHENA e-platform Homepage

The ATHENA e-platform Homepage contains the following information:

- Header highlighting the sections of the e-platform, namely 'Trainings', 'Women researchers', 'ATHENA Toolkit', 'Community' and 'Contact'. A new section named 'ATHENA Toolkit' will be included once, as mentioned in section 2.2, the corresponding deliverable D4.3 on the ATHENA toolkit is submitted. The header appears within all pages of the e-platform.
- A message welcoming visitors to the e-platform and encouraging them to register and join the women researchers database.
- A motivational message to encourage visitors to access the trainings section.
- A carrousel showing the latest trainings included within the e-platform. Topic of each training, its trainer, duration and number of lectures are shown as overview.
- A carrousel presenting the latest women researchers that have been incorporated to the e-platform.
- Feed of the ATHENA social networks Facebook, Instagram and Twitter.
- Carrousel showing the logos of each of the ATHENA consortium members.
- Footer including the acknowledgement to the EC, contact details, privacy and cookies policies and direct access to the ATHENA e-platform sections.

Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 below show the screenshots of the e-platform Homepage.

Figure 2. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (1/4)

athena
gender equality to unlock
research potential

Welcome to ATHENA online learning center

The ATHENA platform was created to help people get knowledge about gender equality and contribute to a fairer and more equal society.

Start learning from our gender experts

Enhance your skills and become an expert

Let's join!

Empower yourself through gender equality

CHANGE MANAGEMENT and GENDER EQUALITY PLANS

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

by **Consulta Europa**

8 hour(s) 2 Lecture(s)

[See more](#)

GENDER EQUALITY IN RESEARCH & INNOVATION

Gender equality in everyday life of the institution

by **UVSK SAV**

1 hour(s) 1 Lecture(s)

[See more](#)

CHANGE MANAGEMENT and GENDER EQUALITY IN RESEARCH & INNOVATION

How to research in academic field

by **JSI**

1 hour(s) 1 Lecture(s)

[See more](#)

Figure 3. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (2/4)

Women researchers database

Carolina

Stay tuned with ATHENA!

Athena Equality to Seguir página 274 seguidores

Tweets by @ATHENA_Equality

Athena Equality Retweeted

EIGE @eurogender

On the occasion of the World Day of #SocialJustice, let's remind ourselves that 54 % of university graduates are women, still...

Is this social justice?

@athenaequality

Follow on Instagram

Load More Posts

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram icons

Figure 4. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (3/4)

Figure 5. ATHENA e-platform Homepage (4/4)

3.2 Trainings section

3.2.1 Main Training page

The 'Trainings' main page incorporates the following information:

- A header message encouraging the visitors to find the training course that best suits their needs.
- A filter to facilitate the search and identification of trainings of interest. Visitors may filter their searches by the following categories:
 - 'Category': this allows the identification of the trainings by its topics.
 - 'Duration': this category filters the hours of duration of the trainings.
 - 'Trainers': this facilitates the search by filtering the organisation which developed the training.
- A 'keyword' tab is also included so visitors may identify specific trainings by including specific main search words.
- List of the trainings included within the e-platform, presenting, for each of them, its topic, the organisation who developed the training, its duration, the number of lectures and the figure on how participants rated the training.
- At the end of the main 'Training' section a contact form is included so visitors may send suggestions on the kind of courses/trainings they are interested in.

Screenshots showing the main page of the 'Training' section are presented below (Figure 6, 7 and Figure 8).

Figure 6. Main Training section (1/3)

Figure 7. Main Training section (2/3)

What kind of courses are you interested in?

Benefits of learning with ATHENA

- Professional Courses
- Interactive Forum
- Expert Researchers

Send your suggestions!

Your Name

Email Address

Phone Number

Comments

0 of 250 max characters.

SEND

Home Privacy policy
Courses Cookies policy
Women researchers
Contact

© Copyright 2021 by ATHENA
Developed by Consulta Europa S.L.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

Figure 8. Main Training section (3/3)

3.2.2 Webpage of a selected training

Once a training within the main training page is identified, logged users of the e-platform may access the selected training by clicking on it. A new webpage will be open containing information on the selected training: topic, description, and lectures. The participant should click on the button 'Do it know!' to access each lecture. The course will be completed once each of its lectures are so.

At the end of the webpage participants may rate the course by clicking in one of the 5 stars rating. The rating results are automatically showed within the training section at the main 'Trainings' page.

Screenshots showing the visual elements of this webpage are presented below in Figure 8.

Welcome to the training!
Are you ready to start learning?
Gender equality to unlock research potential. Empower yourself through gender equality

How to resist gender bias in an academic field
Jobel Health by JSI
1 hour(s) | 1 Lecture(s)
You have reached 0% of this course

Description
Explanation of the basic concepts connected to gender bias: gender equality, gender discrimination, diversity, sexism, (un)equal treatment.
Exploring the specific context of the academic field and explain it through the concepts of gender regime in academic institutions, concepts of power; glass ceiling/glass architecture; masculine domination, homosocial networks, etc.
Work in groups on specific cases of biases (examples of biased behaviour, practice will be collected from the previous activities – interviews, focus groups or internal documents).

Lecture 1 | How to resist gender bias in an academic field | Do it now!

Rate this course!
☆☆☆☆☆ Rate this course

Figure 8. Example of a selected training

Once accessed the selected lecture, a new webpage will appear containing the recording/PPT presentation of the lecture together with, in case, relevant material at the bottom of the site (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Lecture webpage

3.3 ‘Women researchers’ database section

The ‘Women researchers’ database contains the following information:

- An ‘add expert’ button that appears once the mouse pointer is held on the ‘Women researchers’ tab at the menu bar. By clicking on it, logged users of the e-platform may submit profiles of EU women researchers as always as they comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- A message stressing the visibility of the women researchers and introducing the women researchers’ database.
- A request button ‘*Make a female researcher visible*’ encouraging visitors to contribute by submitting profiles of women researchers at European level.
- A carousel showing the latest profiles of the women researchers updated at the e-platform.

- A map aiming at geo-locate each of the profiles included within the database.

Screenshots of the women researchers' database webpage are displayed in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Figure 10. Women researchers' database page 1/2

“Women and girls represent half of the world’s population and, therefore, also half of its potential” (United Nations)

Meet women researchers in your region!

Figure 11. Women researchers' database page 2/2

3.3 'ATHENA Toolkit' section

The 'ATHENA Toolkit' page includes the following information:

- An introductory text explaining the ATHENA Toolkit and its objectives.
- A filter button so visitors may identify specific key resources by its nature, i.e., report, video, training, tool, webinar, etc.
- An accordion structure including the resources and tools of the Toolkit, sorted by the thematic areas addressed and that were described in section 2.2.2.

Screenshots showing this page may be found in Figure 12.

ATHENA Toolkit

The ATHENA Toolkit aims at supporting ATHENA RPOs and RFOs institutions that are in the process of developing their GEPs. For this purpose, the toolkit offers an array of tools and resources that may assist project institutions with examples, guidance and inspiration useful for tailoring their institutional plans. This Toolkit should be used as complement of the *D4.1-Best practice compendium* project deliverable, which introduces relevant measures and actions identified across Europe research organisations for culture transformation and the development of GEPs.

The recommendations, resources and tools included within this toolkit may also serve any other research organisation interested in implementing a transformative change towards gender equality.

Filter by type of resource

- + [Area 1. Work-life balance and organizational culture](#)
- + [Area 2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making](#)
- + [Area 3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression](#)
- + [Area 4. Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content](#)
- + [Area 5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment](#)
- + [Area 6. Gender budgeting](#)
- + [Area 7. Institutional communication](#)
- + [Area 8. Resources about developing and implementing GEPs](#)
- + [Area 9. Other resources](#)

Figure 12. ATHENA Toolkit webpage

3.4 'Community' section

The 'Community' section includes the interactive forum where logged users of the e-platform may discuss on the issues and challenges for progressing towards gender equality in research and innovation and, more specifically, about shared concerns for the GEPs development and implementation.

As described within section 2.2.3, the interactive forum includes the following:

- Three public discussion rooms, being these: 'Challenges (problems/issues) related to gender (in)equalities'; 'Promising initiatives for promoting gender equality and diversity'; 'Q&A interactive forum'.
- 9 private discussions rooms from the ATHENA consortium.

Screenshots displaying the appearance of the public discussion rooms is presented in Figure 13. Interactive public forum.

Gender equality

Home > Community > Gender equality Unsubscribe

This forum is empty

Forum	Topics	Posts	Last Post
Challenges/problems faced related to gender equality?	0	0	No Topics
Promoting initiatives for promoting gender equality and diversity	0	0	No Topics
Q&A Interactive Forum	0	0	No Topics

Oh, hey! No topics were found here.

Create New Topic in "Gender equality"

Your account has the ability to post unrestricted HTML content.

Topic Title (Maximum Length: 80):

Topic Type:

Topic Type:

Topic Status:

Notify me of follow-up replies via email

Home | Courses | Privacy policy | Cookies policy

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416.

Figure 13. Interactive public forum